

DFT and SQMFF Studies on Structures, Stabilities and Vibrational Spectra of Monomers and Dimer of Antibacterial Agent, Nalidixic Acid

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Abstract

In the present work, structures of two monomeric forms and the dimer of Nalidixic acid in accordance to the experimental reported have been theoretically studied by using B3LYP/6-311++G** calculations in gas and methanol environments to predict its reactivities, stabilities and, to perform the assignments of all the normal modes of vibration. Thus, based in the scaled quantum mechanical force field (SQMFF) methodology, the assignments of 168 and 81 normal modes of vibration for the dimer and monomers, respectively have been performed. Very good correlations between experimental and theoretical IR, Raman, and Ultraviolet spectra are acquired evidencing in the same the presence of those three forms of acid, as was experimentally observed. NBO and AIM calculations suggest that both forms present the same stabilities in the gas phase while the form II is less stable in methanol solution. Both studies revealed the existence of intermolecular contacts, as observed in the experimental structures. The form I has a solvation energy of -89.22 kJ/mol, the form II -60.34 kJ/mol and the dimer -73.32 kJ/mol. The present study confirms some of the assignments previously made with some modifications indicated by the most accurate force field developed in the present work. In addition, the scaled force constants are also reported.

Keywords: *Nalidixic acid, vibrational spectra, molecular structure, SQMFF, DFT.*

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Introduction

Nalidixic acid, whose name IUPAC is 1-ethyl-7-methyl-4-oxo-1,8-naphthyridine-3-carboxylic acid, belongs to the group of synthetic quinolones chemotherapeutic agents which are not produced by microorganisms, unlike antibiotics. The frequent use of this drug has led to increased resistance against a wide range of pathogenic bacteria and to augmented attention in its study from different points of view and, obviously, the interest in the design of new quinolone derivatives (Huber, Gowda, & Acharya, 1980; Emmerson, & Jones, 2003; Andriole, 2005; Gunasekaran, et al., 2005; Pavez, Toro-Labbé, & Encinas, 2006; Amin, Mehdinejad, & Pourdangchi, 2009; Drlica, et al., 2009; Muthu, Elamurugu Porchelvi, & Erdogdu, 2011; Gangavaram, et al., 2012; Zhu, et al., 2014; Pandey, et al., 2018; Manin, et al., 2019). Huber et al. (1980) refined the experimental structure of acid while the structures of three polymorphic crystals for the monomer of acid and its dimer by Gangavaram et al. (2012). Two of these three experimental polymorphic forms (I and II) differ in the position of the methylene group while only the experimental X-ray pattern of the remaining form III was presented (Gangavaram et al., 2012). Experimentally, the forms I and II forming the dimeric species of acid (Gangavaram et al., 2012). Photophysics and photochemistry studies of this acid were published by Pavez et al. (2006) while the thermodynamic properties of nalidixic acid was recently reported by Manin et al. (2019). Vibrational studies based in symmetry coordinates of only one monomeric form of acid were published independently by Gunasekaran et al. (2005) and Muthu et al. (2011). Gunasekaran et al. (2005) employed normal coordinate's analysis following the Wilson's F-G matrix method assuming the ethyl and methyl groups as point masses and they have considered naphthalene, anthracene and pyridine for the assignments of fundamental vibrations of monomer of acid. This way, force constants for the acid were also obtained. On the contrary, Muthu et al. have combined HF/6-31G(d,p) and B3LYP/6-31G(d,p) calculations to optimize the

structure of one monomer of acid but the vibrational assignments of the infrared and Raman spectra were obtained with the aid of the *GaussView* program (Drlica, et al., 2009). Thus, in these two latter works, the structural, electronic, topological and vibrational properties of the acid have been not reported yet and only the vibrational analyses were carried out for one monomer of acid. The dimeric species of acid and the scaled quantum mechanical force field (SQMFF) methodology with scaling factors and the Molvib program have been not considered in neither of those two vibrational studies (Pulay, et al., 1983; Rauhut, & Pulay, 1995a 1995b). Consequently, so far, the two monomeric forms and dimeric species of nalidixic acid are not fully characterized. In this context, the aims of this work are: (i) to optimize the two forms I and II of monomer of acid and its dimer in gas phase and methanol solution by using the hybrid B3LYP/6-311++G(d,p) level of theory (Sundius, 2002; Becke, 1988), (ii) to predict stabilities, reactivities and behaviours of acid in the different media, solvation energies, bond orders, molecular electrostatic potentials, and atomic charges (Lee, Yang, & Parr, 1988; Miertuš, Scrocco, & Tomasi, 1981; Tomasi, & Persico, 1994) and, finally (iii) to perform the complete vibrational assignments of monomers and dimer of acid by using the SQMFF methodology, normal internal coordinates, transferable scaling factors and the Molvib program (Pulay, et al., 1983; Rauhut, & Pulay, 1995a 1995b). Here, the scaled force constants of monomers and dimer of acid were compared between them and, also with those reported by Gunasekaran et al. (2005). Comparisons of vibrational assignments performed here for monomers and dimer of acid have been reported. This study shows the importance of producing very good assignments using the experimental structure obtained from X-ray diffraction and adequate methodology for correct and quick identifications of all vibration modes of compound.

Computational Details

At the B3LYP/6-311++G** level of theory, the Gaussian 16 program was used to derive the

optimized geometries of two monomers and dimer of nalidixic acid in the gas and methanol environments (Sundius, 2002; Becke, 1988; Marenich, Cramer, & Truhlar, 2009). The universal solvation continuum model, was used to perform the calculations in solution (Lee, Yang, & Parr, 1988; Miertuš, Scrocco, & Tomasi, 1981; Tomasi, & Persico, 1994) while with the Moldraw program were evaluated changes in the volumes (Frisch, et al., 2009). At the aforementioned level of theory, atomic charges, molecular electrostatic potentials, stabilization energies, bond orders, and intramolecular interactions were calculated using NBO and AIM software's (Ugliengo, 1998; Glendening, et al., 1996; Bader, 1990; Biegler-König, Schönbohm, & Bayles, 2001). Electronic transitions and the frontier orbitals were obtained upon TD-DFT at same level of theory (Besler, Merz Jr, & Kollman, 1990; Brédas, 2014). Using the internal coordinates, scaling factors and SQMFF methodology with the MOLVIB program, the harmonic force fields and the scaled force constants in the above environments have been calculated (Pulay, et al., 1983; Rauhut, & Pulay, 1995a 1995b). Here,

suggested equations (Parr, & Pearson, 1983) were used to convert the expected Raman spectra into intensities. The predicted total energy values have been adjusted using ZPVE (zero-point vibrational energy). Then, the corrected energy values in the different media are compared. BSSE effects using the counterpoise method with B3LYP method is negligible with the larger basis set (6-311++G**), as was also observed for the dimer of 4-hydroxybenzoic acid (Keresztury, al., 1993).

Results and Discussion

Optimizations in Different Phases

Gangavaram et al. (2012) reported the crystal polymorphic structures of three monomeric forms I, II and III and dimer of nalidixic acid. Both forms I and II forming the dimer of acid (Gangavaram et al., 2012). The optimized structures of both monomers at the aforementioned level in gas and methanol environments are depicted in Fig. 1 while the structure of dimer showing each monomer and the intra-molecular H bonds interactions can be seen in Fig. 2.

Figure 1. Molecular Structures of Forms I and II of Nalidixic Acid, Identifications of Rings and Atoms Numbering

Figure 2. Molecular Structure of Dimer of Nalidixic Acid, Identifications of Rings and Atoms Numbering

Table 1 shows the total energy computed with and without zero-point vibrational energy (ZPVE), dipole moments, and volumes for acid in both environments. Additionally, the permittivity values for two media and the variations in energies expressed in Hartrees are listed in this table. Note that the corrections for monomers and dimer by ZPVE (ΔE_{ZPVE}) produce higher energy values or most negative values. The deep analysis of the data show that: (i) both monomeric forms of acid have the same energy and dipole moment values in gas phase

but the form I shows a higher volume than the other one, (ii) in methanol solution, the form I is the most stable with higher dipole moment and volume, as a result of its higher solvation, (iii) the differences in the uncorrected and corrected energy values by using ZPVE show higher values for the form I ($\Delta E = -76.85$ and $\Delta E_{ZPVE} = -79.48$ kJ/mol) and, (iv) the dimeric form evidence a higher stability in solution with a higher volume and practically dipole moment null in the two media.

Table 1. Calculated Total (E) and Corrected by ZPVE Energies (EZPVE), Dipole Moments (μ) and Volumes (V) of Monomers and Dimer of Nalidixic Acid in Gas phase and Methanol Solution by Using B3LYP/6-311++G Level of Theory. Permittivity's (ϵ) Values of All Species are Also Included**

B3LYP/6-311++G** Method							
Monomer Nalidixic acid							
Gas Phase							
Species	E (Hartrees)	E_{ZPVE} (Hartrees)	μ (D)	V (\AA^3)	ϵ	ΔE	ΔE_{ZPVE}
Form I	-799.9575	-799.7308	9.29	237.7	1		
Form II	-799.9575	-799.7307	9.29	234.0			
Methanol Solution							
Form I	-799.9868	-799.7611	13.45	236.8	32.70	-76.85	-79.48
Form II	-799.9759	-799.7497	12.55	234.3		-48.26	-49.84

Monomer Nalidixic acid							
Gas Phase	-1599.9361	-1599.4815	0.02	468.9	1		
Methanol	-1599.9558	-1599.5030	0.008	473.3	32.70	-51.67	-56.39

Note: ZPVE, Zero point vibrational energy

Graphics of dipole moment vectors for the two forms of acid shows that the same are oriented

outside of the centre ring and on the direction of C6-N5 bond, as specified in Fig. 3.

Figure 3. Orientations and Directions of Dipole Moment Vectors for Two Forms of Nalidixic Acid, (upper) Form I and (bottom) form II in Gas Phase and Methanol Solution by Using the B3LYP/6-311++G Level of Theory**

When the dipole moment vectors are analysed it is observed that the orientation, magnitude and direction of those vectors in gas phase are practically similar between them while in methanol solution, the magnitude of vector of form I increase its value and slight changes in the direction and orientation are observed. However, the energy difference between the monomers is null because both forms have the same values in the gas phase while in solution the difference is -28.59 kJ/mol. Then, comparing the sum of two isolated monomers of acid ($-799.9575 \times 2 = -1599.9150$ Hartrees in gas phase

and $-799.9868 + (-799.9558) = -1599.9627$ Hartrees in solution) with the corresponding values predicted in each medium the energy difference is -55.34 kJ/mol in gas phase and -18.09 kJ/mol in methanol. These calculations show that the total energy for dimer is smaller than the sum of the energies of each monomer in gas phase but the difference change in solution. Thus, the presence of dimer even in the gas phase is preferable to the isolated monomer but in solution due to high-energy difference between both forms (28.59 kJ/mol) only the form I and the dimer are expected. This result is

very important to perform later the assignments of all bands observed in the infrared and Raman spectra of nalidixic acid.

B3LYP/6-311++G(d,p) calculations have evidenced that the form I of acid is most stable than the other one in methanol solution with an energy difference higher or more negative and, as a consequence, the solvation energy values

should be predicted for both monomers and its dimer. Table 2 displays the nalidixic acid's uncorrected (ΔG_{un}) and corrected solvation energy value (ΔG_c), and the difference of volumes, which were calculated at the same level of computations. ΔG_{ne} are non-electrostatic terms calculated for each species from the universal solvation continuum model.

Table 2. Corrected Solvation Energies (ΔG_c) in kJ/mol, Volumes Variations (ΔV) of Monomers of Nalidixic Acid and Its Dimer in Methanol Solution by Using B3LYP/6-311++G Level of Theory**

Nalidixic acid in Methanol Solution				
Medium	ΔG_{un} (kJ/mol)	ΔG_{ne}	ΔG_c	$\Delta V(\text{\AA}^3)$
Form I	-76.85	12.37	-89.22	-0.9
Form II	-48.26	12.08	-60.34	0.3
Dimer	-51.67	21.65	-73.32	4.4

Note: ΔG_{ne} is non-electrostatic terms.

Regarding the results for the forms in solution, I and II we observed contraction and expansion of volumes respectively while the dimer shows the higher expansion in methanol with a difference of 4.4\AA^3 . A higher ΔG_c value for the form I in methanol is observed (-89.22 kJ/mol) while the dimer shows a lower value (-73.32 kJ/mol). Thus, the calculated ΔG_c values for antibacterial Nalidixic acid are higher than the solvation energy of antiviral agent as chloroquine in water (-52.06 kJ/mol) and similar to antiviral Niclosamide in water (-78.43 kJ/mol) and oseltamivir in water (-91.50 kJ/mol) (Brandán, et al., 2010; Romano, et al., 2020).

Differences in the values are justified by the different acceptor and donor groups. As a result, antibacterial Nalidixic acid presents only a donor O-H group and five acceptors (O and N atoms) groups while oseltamivir has other donors NH_2 and N-H groups (Romani, et al., 2020).

Geometrical Parameters in Both Environments

Calculated geometrical parameters for the monomers of Nalidixic acid in gas and methanol solution are shown in Table 3 compared with the corresponding experimental ones in the solid phase.

Table 3. Comparison of Calculated Geometrical Parameters for the Monomers of Nalidixic Acid in Gas and Methanol (MeOH) Solution Compared with the Corresponding Experimental Ones in the Solid Phase

B3LYP/6-311++G**a					Exp ^b
Parameters	Form I		Form II		
	Gas	MeOH	Gas	MeOH	
Bond lengths (\AA)					
C11=O1	1.245	1.262	1.245	1.256	1.263(4)
C16=O3	1.210	1.223	1.210	1.218	1.208(3)
N4-C8	1.480	1.487	1.480	1.485	1.484(4)
N4-C6	1.395	1.397	1.395	1.397	1.400(3)

N4-C9	1.351	1.339	1.351	1.342	1.348(3)
N5-C6	1.336	1.334	1.336	1.334	1.352(3)
N5-C13	1.333	1.335	1.333	1.334	1.338(3)
C10-C16	1.500	1.479	1.500	1.487	1.494(4)
C16-O2	1.334	1.335	1.334	1.336	1.334(4)
C6-C7	1.410	1.411	1.410	1.410	1.393(4)
C9=C10	1.369	1.380	1.369	1.377	1.369(4)
C12=C15	1.380	1.377	1.380	1.378	1.360(4)
RMSD	0.011	0.012	0.009	0.010	
Bond Angles (°)					
C8-N4-C9	119.8	119.2	119.8	119.7	119.7(2)
C8-N4-C6	120.6	120.9	120.6	120.6	121.4(2)
N4-C6-N5	117.0	117.0	117.0	116.9	115.1(2)
C9-C10-C16	117.3	118.3	117.3	118.2	117.4(3)
C16-C10-C11	122.6	121.6	122.6	121.8	122.4(3)
C10-C16-O3	122.2	123.9	122.2	123.5	124.4(3)
C10-C11-O1	123.4	122.6	123.4	122.8	123.4(3)
C7-C11-O1	121.7	121.8	121.7	121.9	121.3(3)
N5-C13-C17	116.5	116.8	116.5	116.7	117.2(2)
N4-C8-C14	112.7	112.5	112.7	112.5	113.4(2)
C17-C13-C15	121.5	121.3	121.5	121.3	120.6(3)
C11-C7-C12	121.4	121.9	121.4	121.7	122.6(3)
RMSD	1.0	0.8	1.0	0.9	
Dihedral angles (°)					
C9-C10-C16-O2	179.9	-179.9	179.9	-179.9	-175.1(3)
C9-C10-C11-O1	179.9	179.8	-179.9	-179.9	178.0(3)
C8-N4-C9-C10	-177.9	-178.1	177.9	178.1	-177.3(3)
C6-N5-C13-C17	179.7	-179.6	-179.7	179.9	179.6(2)
RMSD	177.5	179.6	356.9	252.2	

Source: ^aThis work, ^bFrom Gangavaram, et al. (2012)

A detailed structural analysis is necessary to achieve an accurate physical insight of antibacterial capability of nalidixic acid. Gangavaram et al. reported the structural parameters for two forms of acid and its dimer where the form I is different from the form II in the position of the methylene group (Gangavaram, et al., 2012). Experimentally, the forms I and II forming the dimeric species of acid (Gangavaram, et al., 2012). Some structural parameters for the two forms of acid in two environments along with solid state are listed in Table 3. Comparisons between the calculated

optimized structure and their experimental results are shown by using the mean square deviation (RMSD) values. RMSDs values for bond lengths of the two forms are between 0.012 and 0.009 Å while the values for bond angles are between 1.0 and 0.8 ° showing both forms similar parameters and correlations in both media. Then, the dihedral angles show significant differences between the two forms and in both media, as observed by the high RMSDs from Table 3. Thus, the different volume values evidenced by the forms I and II in gas phase are justified by the different signs of

the dihedral C9-C10-C11-O1, C8-N4-C9-C10 and C6-N5-C13-C17 angles. The form I shows a better concordance in the dihedral angles despite the C9-C10-C16-O2 and C6-N5-C13-C1 angles have values and signs different from the corresponding experimental ones.

Analysing from Table 4 the calculated Hydrogen Bonds interactions predicted for the dimer of acid in gas phase and methanol solution by using the B3LYP/6-311++G** method we observed

good correlations in the H...A and D...A distances and <D-H...A angles when they are compared with the experimental values (Gangavaram, et al., 2012). The atoms labelling for the dimer should be observed from Fig. 2. Thus, for the O31-H58...O30 interaction, the predicted H...A distance is 1.645 Å, D...A is 2.573 Å the <D-H...A is 152.3 ° while the experimental values are respectively, 1.61 Å, 2.528 Å and 153 °.

Table 4. Calculated Hydrogen Bonds Interactions Predicted for the Dimer of Acid in Gas Phase and Methanol Solution by Using the B3LYP/6-311++G Method**

B3LYP/6-311++G** Method ^a				
Gas Phase				
Crystal form	Interaction	H...A (Å)	D...A (Å)	<D-H...A (°)
Form I	O31-H58...O30	1.645	2.573	152.3
	C9-H20...O32	2.200	3.231	157.9
	C38-H49...O3	2.200	3.231	157.8
Form II	O2-H29...O1	1.645	2.573	152.4
Methanol Solution				
Form I	O31-H58...O30	1.605	2.546	153.6
	C9-H20...O32	2.298	3.338	160.1
	C38-H49...O3	2.297	3.337	160.2
Form II	O2-H29...O1	1.605	2.546	153.6

Source: ^aThis work

The values for the O31-H58...O30 interaction in solution change to 1.605 Å, 2.546 Å and 153.6 ° showing that the effect of solvation is the increasing in the D...A distances and, for these reasons, the volume of dimer increase in methanol solution.

Charges, Electrostatic Potential, and Bond Order

The different properties of species and its behaviours in various environments can be explained by using the atomic charges, molecular electrostatic potentials (MEP), and bond orders (BO). Hence, Merz-Singh-Kollman (MK), Mulliken and atomic natural population (NPA) charges, along with MEPs and BOs have been computed for donors and acceptors groups (O and N atoms) of both forms of nalidixic acid. Thus, those three types of charges, MEPs and BOs for both forms of acid in gas phase and methanol solution by using the B3LYP/6-

311++G(d,p) method are presented in Table 5. The individual behaviours for MK, Mulliken and NPA charges on the O and N atoms of nalidixic acid in gas phase and methanol environments are shown in Fig. 4. Analysing these graphics, we see that the variations of charges on O and N atoms for the two forms of acid follow approximately the same tendency, with exception of Mulliken charges on O2 because these atoms have less negative values in both media while higher MK and NPA charges (most negative) are observed on these atoms. From Table 5, it is observed that the values of Mulliken charges on O and N atoms are very different from MK and NPA charges. In general, the three charges increase its values in solution. Another interesting observation occur in the O atoms of C=O groups of both forms of acid because the three charges on O1 present most negative values than O3 due to intra-molecular H bonds where those atoms are involved. On the contrary, the MK

and NPA charges on N4 have less negative values than N5 while they show positive Mulliken charges.

Table 5. Mulliken, Merz-Kollman and NPA Charges (a.u.), Molecular Electrostatic Potentials (MEP) (a.u.) and Bond Orders, Expressed as Wiberg Indexes for the Two Monomeric Species of Nalidixic Acid in Gas Phase and in Methanol Solution by Using B3LYP/6-311++G Calculations**

Form I					
Gas Phase					
Atoms	MK	Mulliken	NPA	MEP	BO
1 O	-0.637	-0.357	-0.651	-22.381	1.969
2 O	-0.666	-0.219	-0.680	-22.352	2.009
3 O	-0.595	-0.318	-0.611	-22.404	2.010
4 N	-0.296	0.283	-0.403	-18.298	3.484
5 N	-0.608	0.042	-0.514	-18.377	3.079
Methanol Solution					
Atoms	MK	Mulliken	NPA	MEP	BO
1 O	-0.645	-0.371	-0.657	-22.382	1.965
2 O	-0.668	-0.236	-0.680	-22.361	2.011
3 O	-0.605	-0.331	-0.619	-22.411	1.993
4 N	-0.305	0.296	-0.398	-18.294	3.492
5 N	-0.616	0.038	-0.512	-18.374	3.080
Form II					
Gas Phase					
Atoms	MK	Mulliken	NPA	MEP	BO
1 O	-0.628	-0.357	-0.651	-22.381	1.969
2 O	-0.661	-0.219	-0.680	-22.352	2.009
3 O	-0.594	-0.318	-0.611	-22.404	2.010
4 N	-0.264	0.283	-0.403	-18.298	3.484
5 N	-0.605	0.041	-0.514	-18.377	3.079
Methanol Solution					
Atoms	MK	Mulliken	NPA	MEP	BO
1 O	-0.633	-0.367	-0.654	-22.381	1.970
2 O	-0.662	-0.237	-0.681	-22.360	2.009
3 O	-0.599	-0.327	-0.615	-22.408	2.000
4 N	-0.267	0.292	-0.399	-18.295	3.490
5 N	-0.606	0.040	-0.513	-18.374	3.080

Figure 4. Calculated MK, Mulliken and NPA Charges on O and N Atoms Corresponding to the Two Forms of Nalidixic Acid in Gas Phase and Methanol Solution by Using the B3LYP/6-311++G** Level of Theory

Figure 5. Calculated Electrostatic Potential Surfaces on the Molecular Surfaces of the Two Forms and Dimer of Nalidixic Acid in Gas Phase. B3LYP Functional and 6-311++G** Basis Set. Isodensity Value of 0.005

The MEPs graphs for the two forms of nalidixic acid in gas phase and its dimer at similar level are shown in Fig. 5. Colours red, blue, and green colours on the MEP maps depict various nucleophilic, electrophilic, and neutral regions of reactivity.

The forms I and II show the same colorations and values in gas phase displayed in the identical

areas in both environments (± 0.068 a.u.) but in solution these surfaces evidence different values (± 0.074 a.u. form I while ± 0.072 a.u. form II). Red colours can be seen on the O1-O3 atoms and blue colour on the H29 of OH group. The sections with green colour are neutral sites while the regions with red and blue colours represent nucleophilic and electrophilic sites, respectively. Furthermore, the carbonyl group and the O-H bond are the best places for nalidixic acid as the electrophile and nucleophile positions, respectively. On the other hand, the dimeric species show different values in the two media, as expected due to its solvation, thus, the MEP surface in gas phase show a value of ± 0.048 a.u. that change in solution at ± 0.051 a.u.

Natural Bond Orbital (NBO) and Atoms in Molecules (AIM) Studies

The study of nalidixic acid's stability in the mentioned environments is useful to discuss the antibacterial property because of donor and acceptor groups (N, C=O and O-H groups). As a result, intra-molecular interactions can be predicted by using second-order perturbation theory analyses, $E^{(2)}$; and topological parameters by using NBO and AIM 2000 programs (Ugliengo, 1998; Glendening, et al., 1996; Bader, 1990). Hence, main delocalization energies of both forms of acid in gas phase and methanol solution by using B3LYP/6-311++G** calculations can be seen in Table 6.

Table 6. Main Delocalization Energies (in kJ/mol) of Both Forms of Antibacterial Nalidixic Acid in Gas Phase and Methanol Solution (MOH) by Using B3LYP/6-311++G Calculations**

B3LYP/6-311++G**				
Delocalization	Form I		Form II	
	Gas	MOH	Gas	MOH
$\pi N4-C6 \rightarrow \pi^* C9-C10$	123.94	130.67	123.90	128.99
$\pi N5-C13 \rightarrow \pi^* N4-C6$	169.54	170.34	169.50	170.29
$\pi C9-C10 \rightarrow \pi^* O1-C11$	122.10	131.59	122.06	128.41
$\pi C9-C10 \rightarrow \pi^* O3-C16$	80.84	89.20	80.80	85.98
$\pi C12-C15 \rightarrow \pi^* N5-C13$	128.91	127.41	128.87	127.41
$\Delta E_{\pi \rightarrow \pi^*}$	625.33	649.20	625.12	641.09
$\pi C12-C15 \rightarrow LP(1)C7$	41.49	40.91	41.48	41.03
$\Delta E_{\pi \rightarrow LP^*}$	41.49	40.91	41.48	41.03
$LP(2)O2 \rightarrow \pi^* O3-C16$	212.85	217.15	212.85	215.31
$LP(1)C7 \rightarrow \pi^* O1-C11$	322.11	354.17	322.19	345.52
$LP(1)C7 \rightarrow \pi^* N4-C6$	1184.28	1203.05	1184.74	1201.04
$LP(1)C7 \rightarrow \pi^* C12-C15$	274.63	265.97	274.54	268.23
$\Delta E_{LP \rightarrow \pi^*}$	1993.86	2040.34	1994.32	2030.10
$LP(2)O1 \rightarrow \sigma^* O2-H29$	83.47	118.84	83.47	115.58
$LP(2)O1 \rightarrow \sigma^* C7-C11$	76.12	69.47	76.12	71.23
$LP(2)O1 \rightarrow \sigma^* C10-C11$	52.58	42.93	52.58	45.02
$LP(2)O3 \rightarrow \sigma^* O2-C16$	123.60	117.21	123.60	
$LP(2)O3 \rightarrow \sigma^* C10-C16$	79.29	74.11	79.34	
$\Delta E_{LP \rightarrow \sigma^*}$	415.07	422.56	415.12	231.82
$\pi^* N4-C6 \rightarrow \pi^* N5-C13$	348.74	344.77	348.65	345.39
$\pi^* N4-C6 \rightarrow \pi^* C9-C10$	126.57	139.24	126.53	134.89
$\pi^* N5-C13 \rightarrow \pi^* C12-C15$	519.45	476.56	518.49	487.47
$\pi^* C9-C10 \rightarrow \pi^* O3-C16$	349.32	307.19	349.28	304.47
$\Delta E_{\pi^* \rightarrow \pi^*}$	1344.08	1267.75	1342.95	1272.22
ΔE_{TOTAL}	4419.83	4420.76	4418.99	4216.26

We observed five different interactions in the aforementioned environments for the donor-acceptor interactions of nalidixic acid in both phases, including $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$, $\pi \rightarrow n$, $LP \rightarrow \pi^*$, $LP \rightarrow \sigma^*$ and $\pi^* \rightarrow \pi^*$ interactions. Evaluating the total energy of these interactions, clearly the form II of acid is less stable in solution than the other one, as was previously analysed in Table 1. Hence, in methanol, the $LP(2)O3 \rightarrow \sigma^* O2-C16$ and $LP(2)O3 \rightarrow \sigma^* C10-C16$ interactions in the form II are not observed. However, thus, the two forms in gas phase present practically the

same total energy values. The dimer of acid in gas phase shows a strong $\pi O3-C16 \rightarrow \pi^* C43-H51$ interaction with participation of $C16=O3$ and $H51$ of CH_3 group that disappear in solution.

The topological parameters of bond critical points (BCPs) and ring critical points (RCPs) have been predicted for monomeric and dimer forms of acid by the AIM results. Therefore, the electron density, laplacian value, eigenvalues of Hessian matrix and ratio ($\rho(r), \nabla^2 \rho(r), \lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3$, and $|\lambda_1|/|\lambda_3|$) for both forms in gas phase and methanol solution were listed in the Table 7.

Table 7. Analysis of the Bond Critical Points (BCPs) and Ring critical Point (RCPs) for the Two Monomeric Forms of Antibacterial Nalidixic Acid in Gas Phase and Methanol Solution (MOH) by Using B3LYP/6-311++G Calculations**

Form I/Gas Phase				
Parameter [#]	RCP1	RCP2	RCPN	O2-H29...O1
$\rho(r)$	0.0204	0.0238	0.0192	0.0481
$\nabla^2\rho(r)$	0.1452	0.1706	0.1139	0.1363
$ \lambda_1 / \lambda_3 $	0.1688	0.2047	0.2237	0.2719
Distances				1.700
Form I/Methanol Solution				
Parameter [#]	RCP1	RCP2	RCPN	O2-H29...O1
$\rho(r)$	0.0206	0.0238	0.0206	0.0598
$\nabla^2\rho(r)$	0.1472	0.1702	0.1255	0.1523
$ \lambda_1 / \lambda_3 $	0.1710	0.2048	0.2273	0.2965
Distances				1.611
Form II/Gas Phase				
Parameter [#]	RCP1	RCP2	RCPN	O2-H29...O1
$\rho(r)$	0.0204	0.0238	0.0192	0.0481
$\nabla^2\rho(r)$	0.1452	0.1706	0.1139	0.1363
$ \lambda_1 / \lambda_3 $	0.1687	0.2052	0.2237	0.2718
Distances				1.700
Form II/Methanol Solution				
Parameter [#]	RCP1	RCP2	RCPN	O2-H29...O1
$\rho(r)$	0.0205	0.0238	0.0206	0.0589
$\nabla^2\rho(r)$	0.1465	0.1704	0.1249	0.1515
$ \lambda_1 / \lambda_3 $	0.1700	0.2047	0.2255	0.2945
Distances				1.617

Note: [#] Parameters in a.u., Distances in Å

Molecular graphics of monomeric forms I and II of nalidixic acid and its dimer in gas phase showing their H bonds interactions by using the B3LYP/6-311++G** method can be seen in Fig. 6. For the two monomers in both environments, there are new O2-H29...O1 bonds or BCPs, as shown in Fig. 6 and, therefore

one new RCPNs is formed in each form. These H bonds, with a ratio of $\lambda_1/\lambda_3 < 1$, are ionic or strongly polar covalent bonds. Besides, due to the two A1 and A2 rings are expected 2 RCPs in each one. Analysing the molecular graphic of dimer are observed six new BCPs in this species, four RCP and five new RCPNs.

Figure 6. Molecular Graphics of Monomeric Forms I and II of Nalidixic Acid (upper) and Its Dimer(bottom) in Gas Phase Showing Their H Bonds Interactions by Using the B3LYP/6-311++G Method**

Hence, the dimeric species of acid is very stable. The topological properties of RCP2 of form I of acid are higher than RCP1 while the densities of new O2-H29...O1 bonds of both forms present higher values in methanol probably due to the lower distances between the involved H29 and O1 atoms. These analyses show good stabilities of three species of acid due to the H bonds interactions and to its topological properties.

HOMO–LUMO and Quantum Chemical Global Descriptors

According to Parr and Pearson (1983), the gap values are computed to estimate reactivities from the differences between the highest occupied molecular orbital, HOMO, and the lowest

unoccupied molecular orbital, LUMO. Global descriptors are used to predict the behaviours of molecules (Keresztury, et al., 1993; Brandán, et al., 2010; Romano, et al., 2020; Romani, et al., 2020; Vakili, et al., 2021). The band gaps between HOMO and LUMO, chemical potential (μ), electronegativity (χ), global hardness(η), global softness (S) and global electrophilicity index (ω) (Keresztury, et al., 1993; Brandán, et al., 2010; Romano, et al., 2020; Romani, et al., 2020; Vakili, et al., 2021) for Nalidixic acid in both environments are described in this study and along with the corresponding equations used for calculate them, provided in Table 8.

Table 8. Frontier Molecular Orbitals, HOMO and LUMO, Gap Values and Descriptors for the Two Monomeric Species of Antibacterial Nalidixic Acid in Gas Phase and Methanol Solution (MOH) by Using B3LYP/6-311++G Calculations**

Nalidixic acid ^a						
B3LYP/6-311++G** Method ^a						
Orbital	Form I		Form II		Dimer	
	Gas	MOH	Gas	MOH	Gas	MOH
HOMO	-6.9416	-6.9770	-6.9416	-6.9770	-6.7675	-6.7892
LUMO	-2.4898	-2.5742	-2.4898	-2.5524	-2.2885	-2.3239
GAP	4.4518	4.4028	4.4518	4.4246	4.4790	4.4654
Descriptors						
χ	4.7157	4.7756	4.7157	4.7647	4.528	4.55655

μ	-4.7157	-4.7756	-4.7157	-4.7647	-4.528	-4.55655
η	2.2259	2.2014	2.2259	2.2123	2.2395	2.23265
S	0.2246	0.2271	0.2246	0.2260	0.2233	0.2239
ω	4.9952	5.1800	4.9952	5.1309	4.5775	4.6497
Amantadine ^b						
Orbital	FREE BASE		CATIONIC		HYDROCHLORIDE	
	Gas	Water	Gas	Water	Gas	Water
HOMO	-6.4736	-6.5552	-11.6029	-11.5730	-6.3294	-6.4736
LUMO	-0.4218	-0.4299	-4.9253	-4.9606	-0.9334	-0.4218
GAP	6.0518	6.1253	6.6776	6.6124	5.3960	4.1116
Descriptors						
χ	-3.0259	-3.0627	-3.3388	-3.3062	-2.6980	-2.0558
μ	-3.4477	-3.4926	-8.2641	-8.2668	-3.6314	-3.3130
η	3.0259	3.0627	3.3388	3.3062	2.6980	2.0558
S	0.1652	0.1633	0.1498	0.1512	0.1853	0.2432
ω	1.9641	1.9914	10.2275	10.3351	2.4439	2.6695

Source: ^aThis work, ^bFrom Rauhut, & Pulay, (1995)

Note: $\chi = - [E(\text{LUMO}) - E(\text{HOMO})]/2$; $\mu = [E(\text{LUMO}) + E(\text{HOMO})]/2$; $\eta = [E(\text{LUMO}) - E(\text{HOMO})]/2$; $S = 1/2\eta$; $\omega = \mu^2/2\eta$

These results with the corresponding to the three species of antiviral amantadine agent in the same table are compared (Brandán, 2021). Evaluating first both forms of acid, it is observed that in gas phase both forms present the same reactivity (4.4518 eV), however, in solution the form I is most reactive than the other one due to its lower gap value (4.4028 eV). Note that the dimer of acid in both media is less reactive than the monomers ones. If now the values are compared with the species of amantadine it is observed that the hydrochloride form is the most reactive with the lower gap value (4.1116 eV) while the reactivity of other antiviral chloroquine (4.4571 eV) is similar to both forms of Nalidixic acid in gas phase (Brandán, et al., 2010). Larger values of ω in Nalidixic acid and amantadine could help to understand the difference between the different gap values (Vakili, et al., 2021).

Ultraviolet-Visible Spectra

Predicted electronic spectra of both forms of nalixic acid in methanol solution by using the B3LYP/6-311++G** method are shown in Figure 7 compared with the experimental in acetone (Brandán, 2021). Experimentally, the nalidixic acid dissolved in pure acetone shows 2

peaks at 210 and 340 nm respectively but when increase the water quantity the peak at 340 nm is shifted at lower wavelength and transformed in two new peaks due to the hypsochromic effect of the water (Brandán, 2021).

Figure 7. Predicted Electronic Spectra of Both Monomers and Dimer Forms of Nalidixic Acid in Methanol Solution by Using the B3LYP/6-311++G** Method Compared with the Experimental in Acetone

Source: Muñoz, Palacio, & Rivas, (2020).

Obviously, this behavior is associated to the H-bond interaction between the acid and the water. The calculated wavelengths obtained in the methanol solution shows two bands at 245 and 325 nm evidencing a reasonable correlation with the experimentally observed. Note that despite the form I is most stable in solution apparently the form II is also present in solution together with the dimer. The bands could be assigned to $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ and $LP \rightarrow \pi^*$ interaction predicted by NBO calculations.

Vibrational Study

This analysis was performed for the three species of nalidixic acid because they were experimentally observed in the solid phase and, besides due to the similarity in the predicted UV spectra for the two forms in methanol solution, probably both species are in this medium too. Both monomeric forms of acid were optimized with C_1 symmetries as its dimeric form. For the monomers are expected 81 vibration modes while for the dimer 168 modes where all of them present activity in both IR and Raman spectra.

Figs 8 and 9 show the experimental IR and Raman spectra taken from the literature (Bio-Rad Laboratories, n.d.) compared with the predicted for the two forms of acid and its dimer in gas phase by using B3LYP/6-311++G** calculations. The figures show very good correlations and evidence the presence of the three forms of acid. The complete assignments of species were performed with the calculated harmonic force fields using the SQMFF methodology, normal internal coordinates, transferable scaling factors and the Molvib program. Observed and calculated wavenumbers and assignments for both forms of nalidixic acid and its dimer in gas phase by using B3LYP/6-311++G** method can be seen in Table 9. The forms I and II of acid show practically the same predicted IR spectra, however, the Raman spectrum for the Form II present a strong band at 1610 cm^{-1} not evidenced in the form I and, the which justify the strong experimental band observed in that position. Below, a brief discussion of some assignments are presented by regions.

Figure 8. Experimental Infrared Spectrum for Nalidixic Acid in the Solid Phase (Bio-Rad Laboratories, n.d.) Compared with the Predicted for Both Forms and Its Dimer in Gas Phase by Using the B3LYP/6-311++G Method**

Figure 9. Experimental Raman Spectrum for Nalidixic Acid in the Solid Phase (Bio-Rad Laboratories, n.d.) Compared with the Predicted for Both Forms and Its Dimer in Gas Phase by Using the B3LYP/6-311++G Method**

Table 9. Observed and Calculated Wavenumbers (cm⁻¹) and Assignments for Both Forms of Nalidixic Acid and Its Dimer in Gas Phase by Using B3LYP/6-311++G Method**

Experimental ^a		B3LYP/6-311++G** Method ^a					
		Form I		Form II		Dimer	
ATR	Raman	SQM	Assignments ^a	SQM	Assignments ^a	SQM	Assignments ^a
3157w		3126	vO2-H29	3127	vO2-H29	3070	vC41-H50
3060sh	3064w	3069	vC12-H21	3070	vC12-H21	3070	vC12-H21
3044w	3055sh	3066	vC9-H20	3067	vC9-H20	3057	vC38-H49
		3056	vC15-H25	3056	vC15-H25	3055	vC15-H25
	3034sh					3055	vC44-H54
						3055	vC9-H20
	3028w					3022	v _a CH ₂ (C8)
3000w		3012	v _a CH ₂	3013	v _a CH ₂	3022	v _a CH ₂ (C37)
	2990w	2992	v _a CH ₃ (C17)	2993	v _a CH ₃ (C17)	2991	v _a CH ₃ (C46)
						2991	v _a CH ₃ (C17)
						2990	vO2-H29
2982w	2986sh	2987	v _a CH ₃ (C14)	2988	v _a CH ₃ (C14)	2989	vO31-H58
						2985	v _a CH ₃ (C43),v _a CH ₃ (C43)
						2984	v _a CH ₃ (C14),v _a CH ₃ (C14)
						2977	v _a CH ₃ (C43),v _a CH ₃ (C43)
	2971w	2971	v _a CH ₃ (C14)	2971	v _a CH ₃ (C14)	2977	v _a CH ₃ (C14),v _a CH ₃ (C14)
						2966	v _a CH ₃ (C46)
		2965	v _a CH ₃ (C17)	2965	v _a CH ₃ (C17)	2965	v _s CH ₂ (C37)
						2965	v _s CH ₂ (C8)
						2965	v _a CH ₃ (C17)
2943w	2930w	2949	v _s CH ₂	2950	v _s CH ₂	2912	v _s CH ₃ (C46)
						2912	v _s CH ₃ (C17)
2913w	2912m	2912	v _s CH ₃ (C17)	2912	v _s CH ₃ (C14)	2912	v _s CH ₃ (C43)
2913w		2911	v _s CH ₃ (C14)	2912	v _s CH ₃ (C17)	2912	v _s CH ₃ (C14)
1704s	1709s	1726	vC16=O3	1727	vC16=O3	1699	0
						1697	vC45=O32
1611s	1607vs	1601	vC9-C10	1601	vC11=O1,vC9-	1599	vC38-C39
						1595	vC9-C10
		1588	vC12-C15	1588	vC12-C15,vN5-C6	1588	βR ₂ (A2), βR ₂ (A4)
						1586	vC41-C44,vC12-C15
1554w	1554m	1557	vC11=O1	1556	vC11=O1,vC9-	1550	vC40=O30
						1549	vC11=O1
1530w	1537m	1525	vC13-C15,vC7-	1525	vC13-C15,vC7-	1524	vC42-C44,vC36-C41
	1513w					1524	vC13-C15
1506m						1484	vN33-C35
1463s	1464m	1477	vN5-C13,vN4-C6	1478	vN5-C13,vN4-C6	1483	vN5-C13
						1446	δ _a CH ₃ (C43), δCH ₂ (C37)
	1441m	1443	δ _a CH ₃ (C14)	1443	δ _a CH ₃ (C14)	1445	δ _a CH ₃ (C14), δCH ₂ (C8)
1437vs						1434	δ _a CH ₃ (C43), δO31-H58
						1431	δ _a CH ₃ (C14), δ _a CH ₃ (C43)
						1429	δO31-H58
		1429	δ _a CH ₃ (C14)	1430	δ _a CH ₃ (C14)	1429	δ _a CH ₃ (C14), δO2-H29
						1427	δ _a CH ₃ (C43), δ _a CH ₃ (C46)

		1425	$\delta_a\text{CH}_3(\text{C17})$	1425	$\delta_a\text{CH}_3(\text{C17})$	1427	$\delta_a\text{CH}_3(\text{C14}), \delta_a\text{CH}_3(\text{C17})$
						1422	$\delta_a\text{CH}_3(\text{C17}), \delta\text{CH}_2(\text{C8})$
		1424	δCH_2	1424	δCH_2	1422	$\delta_a\text{CH}_3(\text{C46})$
		1419	$\delta\text{CH}_2, \nu\text{C6-C7}$	1419	$\delta\text{CH}_2, \nu\text{C6-C7}$	1415	$\delta_a\text{CH}_3(\text{C17}), \delta_a\text{CH}_3(\text{C17})$
						1415	$\delta_a\text{CH}_3(\text{C46})$
	1411w	1415	$\delta_a\text{CH}_3(\text{C17})$	1415	$\delta_a\text{CH}_3(\text{C17})$	1415	$\delta_a\text{CH}_3(\text{C46})$
1402m		1401	δOH	1401	δOH	1414	$\delta\text{O31-H58}, \delta\text{O2-H29}$
						1383	wagCH ₂ (C8)
1378w	1376s	1379	wagCH ₂	1380	wagCH ₂	1383	wagCH ₂ (C37)
						1359	$\rho\text{CH}_2(\text{C37})$
1363m						1358	$\beta\text{C9-H20}$
		1353	$\delta_s\text{CH}_3(\text{C17})$	1353	$\delta_s\text{CH}_3(\text{C14})$	1350	$\delta_s\text{CH}_3(\text{C17}), \delta_s\text{CH}_3(\text{C46})$
	1348w	1349	$\delta_s\text{CH}_3(\text{C14})$	1349	$\delta_s\text{CH}_3(\text{C17})$	1350	$\delta_s\text{CH}_3(\text{C46}), \delta_s\text{CH}_3(\text{C17})$
						1346	$\delta_s\text{CH}_3(\text{C43})$
1342m		1346	$\nu\text{C10-C11}$	1347	$\nu\text{C10-C11}$	1346	$\delta_s\text{CH}_3(\text{C14})$
	1327s	1339	$\nu\text{N5-C6}$	1339	$\nu\text{N5-}$	1339	$\beta\text{C9-H20}$
						1337	$\beta\text{C38-H49}, \beta\text{C9-H20}$
1315w						1314	$\nu\text{N5-C6}, \nu\text{N5-C13}$
	1291s	1310	$\nu\text{N5-C13}, \nu\text{N5-C6}$	1310	$\nu\text{N5-C13}, \nu\text{N5-C6}$	1313	$\nu\text{N34-C35}, \nu\text{N34-C42}$
1287m						1271	$\nu\text{C6-C7}$
	1272m					1270	$\nu\text{C35-C36}$
1264m	1261sh	1264	$\nu\text{C6-C7}, \nu\text{N5-C13}$	1264	$\nu\text{C6-C7}, \nu\text{N5-C13}$	1265	$\rho\text{CH}_2(\text{C8}), \nu\text{N4-C9}$
1257sh		1255	$\rho\text{CH}_2, \nu\text{N4-C9}$	1256	$\rho\text{CH}_2, \nu\text{N4-C9}$	1263	$\rho\text{CH}_2(\text{C37}), \nu\text{N33-C38}$
						1243	$\beta\text{C38-H49}, \nu\text{C42-C46}$
1241m	1226w	1235	$\nu\text{C13-C17}$	1235	$\beta\text{C9-H20}, \nu\text{C13-C17}$	1243	$\beta\text{C9-H20}, \beta\text{R}_1(\text{A2})$ $\nu\text{C13-C17}$
						1213	$\beta\text{C15-H25}, \nu\text{C7-C12}$ $\nu\text{N4-C6}$
1217m		1215	$\nu\text{N4-C6}$	1215	$\beta\text{C15-H25}, \nu\text{N4-C6}$	1212	$\beta\text{C44-H54}, \nu\text{N33-C35}$
1192sh	1198w					1184	$\nu\text{C45-O31}$
		1175	$\nu\text{C16-O2}$	1174	$\nu\text{C16-O2}, \nu\text{C10-}$	1182	$\nu\text{C16-O2}$
1142sh	1151w	1131	$\beta\text{C12-H21}$	1131	$\beta\text{C12-H21}, \nu\text{C16-}$	1137	$\beta\text{C41-H50}$
1118m	1127w					1137	$\beta\text{C12-H21}$
1091w	1098sh	1102	$\rho\text{CH}_3(\text{C14}), \nu\text{N4-}$	1102	$\rho\text{CH}_3(\text{C14}), \nu\text{N4-}$	1103	$\rho\text{CH}_3(\text{C43})$
	1092w					1101	$\beta\text{C41-H50}$
1083w		1085	$\beta\text{R}_1(\text{A2})$	1085	$\beta\text{R}_1(\text{A2})$	1086	$\beta\text{R}_1(\text{A2})$
						1086	$\beta\text{R}_1(\text{A4})$
						1079	$\rho\text{CH}_3(\text{C43}), \rho\text{CH}_3(\text{C14})$
1076sh	1053w	1076	$\rho\text{CH}_3(\text{C14})$	1077	$\rho\text{CH}_3(\text{C14})$	1079	$\rho\text{CH}_3(\text{C14}), \rho\text{CH}_3(\text{C43})$
1041w		1032	$\rho\text{CH}_3(\text{C17})$	1032	$\rho\text{CH}_3(\text{C17})$	1031	$\rho\text{CH}_3(\text{C17})$
						1031	$\rho\text{CH}_3(\text{C46})$
						1025	$\gamma\text{C9-H20}, \gamma\text{C38-H49}$
1025w		1026	$\nu\text{N4-C8}$	1027	$\nu\text{N4-C8}$	1025	$\nu\text{N33-C37}$
						1016	$\gamma\text{C38-H49}, \tau\text{O3-H49}$
						1007	$\gamma\text{C9-H20}, \gamma\text{C38-H49}$
	1006w	1005	$\rho\text{CH}_3(\text{C17})$	1005	$\rho\text{CH}_3(\text{C17})$	1005	$\rho\text{CH}_3(\text{C46}), \rho\text{CH}_3(\text{C17})$
		1003	$\gamma\text{C12-H21}$	1003	$\gamma\text{C12-H21}$	1002	$\gamma\text{C9-H20}, \gamma\text{C38-H49}$
996w	986sh					1000	$\gamma\text{C41-H50}, \gamma\text{C12-H21}$
959s	968w	966	$\gamma\text{C9-H20}$	967	$\gamma\text{C9-H20}$	999	$\gamma\text{C9-H20}$

950m	937w	936	vC8-C14	937	vC8-C14	940	vC37-C43,vC8-C14
						938	γ C9-H20, γ C38-H49
						928	vC13-C15
929sh		925	vC13-C15, β R ₁ (A2)	925	vC13-C15, β R ₁ (A2)	927	vC42-C44
	905w					858	vC39-C45
864w	877w	854	vC10-C16	854	vC10-C16	858	vC10-C16,vN4-C8
	850w					836	γ C15-H25
837w		837	γ C15-H25	837	γ C15-H25	836	γ C44-H54
						814	τ O2-H29
794vs	805w					814	τ O31-H58
	781s	777	γ COO	777	τ R ₁ (A1), γ COO	779	τ R ₁ (A3)
		776	τ R ₁ (A1), τ OH	776	τ OH	778	τ R ₁ (A1)
768w	770sh	772	β R ₁ (A1)	772	β R ₁ (A1)	770	β R ₁ (A1), β R ₁ (A3)
						770	β C39-C45
						760	γ COO(C45), γ COO(C16)
						758	τ wCH ₂ (C37)
		750	τ wCH ₂ ,	751	τ wCH ₂ ,	754	γ COO(C16), τ R ₁ (A2)
748w		747	τ R ₁ (A2)	747	τ R ₁ (A2)	754	γ COO(C45), τ wCH ₂ (C8), ρ CH ₃ (C14)
						706	δ COO(C45)
	709s	703	δ COO	703	δ COO	706	δ COO(C16)
694m	697s	696	δ COO, β R ₃ (A2)	696	δ COO, β R ₃ (A2)	696	β R ₃ (A4), δ COO(C45)
						696	β R ₃ (A2), δ COO(C16)
						688	γ C40=O30
		680	γ C11=O1	680	γ C11=O1	685	γ C11=O1
	659w					652	β C40=O30
644m	638w	649	β R ₂ (A2)	649	β R ₂ (A2)	651	β C11=O1
						627	τ R ₃ (A4)
625m		622	γ C13-C17, τ R ₃ (A2) τ R ₂ (A2)	623	γ C13-C17, τ R ₃ (A2)	625	τ R ₃ (A2)
574w	561m					553	β R ₃ (A2)
557w	540m	550	β R ₃ (A2)	550	β R ₃ (A2)	551	β R ₃ (A4)
						534	δ N4C8C14
529w		533	δ N4C8C14	532	δ N4C8C14	532	δ N33C37C43
	507w					507	τ R ₃ (A3), τ R ₃ (A1)
491w	488m	503	β R ₂ (A1)	504	β R ₂ (A1)	506	β R ₂ (A1), β R ₂ (A3)
						480	τ R ₃ (A3)
473s	462m	476	τ R ₃ (A1), τ R ₁ (A1)	476	τ R ₃ (A1), τ R ₁ (A1)	477	τ R ₃ (A1)
444m		442	ρ COO	442	ρ COO	448	ρ COO(C45)
433sh	431m					447	ρ COO(C16)
						422	τ R ₂ (A4), τ R ₂ (A2)
420w		419	τ R ₂ (A2)	419	τ R ₂ (A2)	420	τ R ₂ (A2), τ R ₂ (A4)
	403sh					401	β C42-C46
392s	394m	392	β C11=O1, β C13-	392	β C11=O1	400	τ R ₃ (A1)
						379	τ R ₃ (A3), γ C39-C45
372m	377w	372	τ R ₃ (A1), γ C10-C16	372	τ R ₃ (A1)	377	τ R ₃ (A1), γ C10-C16
						369	β N33-C37, β N4-C8
		362	β N4-C8	363	β N4-C8	367	β N4-C8, β N33-C37
	318vs					304	β R ₃ (A3)

	297sh	298	$\beta R_3(A1)$	298	$\beta R_3(A1), \nu C10-C16$ $\nu C7-C11$	302	$\beta R_3(A1), \beta R_3(A3),$ $\nu C7-C11, \nu C36-C40$
						281	$\tau R_3(A1), \tau R_3(A3)$
		279	ButtC6-C7	279	ButtC6-C7	281	$\tau R_3(A3), \tau R_1(A3)$
	264sh					269	$\beta C13-C17$
	251w	259	$\beta C10-C16$	259	$\beta C13-C17$	262	$\beta C39-C45, \beta C10-C16$
						238	$\gamma C10-C16, \gamma C39-C45$ $\tau R_2(A1), \tau R_2(A3)$
	214w	235	$\tau R_2(A1), \gamma C10-C16$	235	$\tau R_2(A1), \gamma C10-C16$	237	$\gamma C39-C45, \gamma C10-C16$
						195	$\gamma C39-C45, \gamma C10-C16$
		190	$\tau_w CH_3(C14), \gamma C10-$	192	$\tau_w CH_3(C14)$	190	$\tau O32-H20, \tau O3-H49$
	186w	189	$\tau_w CH_3(C14)$	189	$\gamma C10-C16$	189	$\tau_w CH_3(C43), \tau_w CH_3(C14)$
						188	$\tau_w CH_3(C14), \tau_w CH_3(C43)$
						176	$\beta C39-C45, \beta C10-C16$
	166w	170	$\beta C10-C16$	170	$\beta C10-C16$	174	$\beta C10-C16, \beta C39-C45$
	149w					119	$\tau_w COO(C16), \tau_w COO(C45)$
		112	$\tau OH, \tau_w COO$	112	$\tau OH, \tau_w COO$	117	$\tau_w COO(C45), \tau_w COO(C16)$
						96	$\tau O3-H49, \tau O32-H20$
		93	$\gamma N4-C8$	94	$\gamma N4-C8$	95	$\gamma N33-C37$
						79	$\tau_w COO(C16)$
		74	$\tau_w COO$	74	$\tau_w COO$	78	$\tau_w COO(C45)$
						71	$\tau O3-H49, \tau O32-H20$
						66	$\tau_w C37-N33, \tau_w C8-N4$
				61	$\tau_w C8-N4$	63	$\nu O3-H49, \nu O32-H20$
		55	$\tau_w C8-N4$			56	$\tau O3-H49, \tau O32-H20$
						53	$\tau O32-H20, \tau O3-H49$
		48	$\tau R_2(A1)$	49	$\tau R_2(A1)$	46	$\delta O32H20C9, \delta O3H49C38$
				42	$\tau_w CH_3(C17), \gamma C13-$	42	$\tau_w CH_3(C17), \gamma C13-C17$
						41	$\tau_w CH_3(C46), \gamma C42-C46$
		32	$\tau_w CH_3(C17)$			36	$\nu O3-H49, \nu O32-H20$
						25	$\tau O32-H20, \tau O3-H49$
						14	$\tau O32-H20, \tau O3-H49$
						7	$\tau O32-H20$

Abbreviations: ν , stretching; β , deformation in the plane; γ , deformation out of plane; wag, wagging; τ , torsion; ρ , rocking; τ_w , twisting; δ , deformation; a, antisymmetric; s, symmetric

Source: ^aThis work

Note: ^bCalculated with B3LYP/6-311++G** method, ^cFrom scaled quantum mechanics force field with B3LYP/6-311++G** method.

Assignments. Region 4000-2000 cm^{-1} . In this region at higher wavenumber are assigned the OH stretching modes of both monomers while in the dimer these modes are forming H bonds and, for these reasons, they are assigned as predicted by SQM calculations to the weak IR band at 2982 cm^{-1} . Note that in the IR spectrum

of dimer the band attributed to those stretching mode is most intense (See Fig. 8). Besides, in this region both forms of acid show practically the same assignments, with exception of symmetrical stretching modes of the two CH_3 groups. In this region are also assigned the CH , CH_2 and CH_3 stretching modes where the

Raman band of medium intensity is assigned to symmetrical modes.

Region 2000-1000 cm^{-1} . In the region between 1720 and 1600 cm^{-1} in the predicted Raman spectrum of form II of acid, the band at 1610 cm^{-1} is most intense than the other monomer and, hence, the presence of this form justify the higher intensity of that band in the experimental spectrum. The presence of dimer is justified by the intense IR and Raman bands at 1704 and 1709 cm^{-1} assigned to C=O stretching modes of three forms of acid. The SQM calculations predict some vibration modes of form II coupled with other stretching modes, as detailed in Table 9. Thus, some C-C stretching modes predicted in this region are mixed with N-C and C=O stretching modes. The OH deformation modes in the monomers are predicted at 1401 cm^{-1} due to the intramolecular H bonds while in the dimer at 1414 cm^{-1} and, for the same reason, the C-O stretching mode are predicted in the monomers at 1175/1174 cm^{-1} while in the dimer at 1182 cm^{-1} . The antisymmetric and symmetric CH_2 and CH_3 deformation modes are predicted in the expected regions (Romani, et al., 2020; Vakili, et al., 2021).

Region below 1000 cm^{-1} . In this region, the vibration modes of dimer are predicted by calculations coupled with other modes while few modes are observed as pure modes. In the monomers only some modes are observed mixed with other, such as CH_3 rocking modes with twisting CH_2 modes at 751/750 cm^{-1} . In the dimer the torsion OH modes are predicted at 814 cm^{-1} while in both monomeric forms due to

the intramolecular H bonds appear at 776 cm^{-1} . Some torsion or deformation modes of some rings are observed coupled in monomer and dimer with similar modes or out-of-plane C-C deformation or C-C stretching modes. The deformation and torsion modes of different rings are predicted by SQM calculations in the expected regions (Keresztury, et al., 1993; Brandán, et al., 2010; Romano, et al., 2020).

Force Constants

Scaled force constants for both monomeric and dimer forms of nalidixic acid were calculated by using B3LYP/6-311++G** calculations taking into account the harmonic force fields computed with the SQMFF methodology and the MOLVIB program (Pulay, et al., 1983; Rauhut, & Pulay, 1995a 1995b). Table 10 shows the force constants of three species expressed in terms of simple valence internal coordinates while the variations of constants are shown in Fig. 10. These results are compared in the table with the obtained by Gunasekaran et al. (2005). Note that our values are different from those reported because they assuming the ethyl and methyl groups as point masses and have considered naphthalene, anthracene and pyridine for the assignments of fundamental vibrations of monomer of acid. The force constants values for the form I are practically similar to form II and only some constants change slightly in solution. The graphic shows that the $f(\nu\text{O-H})$, $f(\nu\text{C=O})$ and $f(\nu\text{C-O})$ force constants decrease in solution as a consequence of solvation of those involved donor and acceptors groups.

Table 10. Scaled Internal Force Constants for the Monomers of Nalidixic Acid and Its Dimer in Gas and Methanol (MOH) Solution Compared with the Corresponding Experimental Ones in the Solid Phase

Force constant	B3LYP/6-311++G** method ^a						Exp ^b
	Form I		Form II		Dimer		
	GAS	Methanol	GAS	Methanol	GAS	Methanol	
$f(\nu\text{O-H})$	5.41	4.44	5.42	4.59	4.92	4.48	5.81
$f(\nu\text{C=O})$	10.67	9.48	10.67	9.94	10.37	9.88	10.08
$f(\nu\text{C-N})_{R1}$	5.67	5.71	5.68	5.70	5.71	5.71	
$f(\nu\text{C-N})_{R2}$	7.08	7.02	7.08	7.04	7.09	7.05	
$f(\nu\text{C-O})$	6.33	5.99	6.33	6.15	6.48	6.19	4.19
$f(\nu\text{CH}_2)$	4.90	4.95	4.90	4.94	4.94	4.95	
$f(\nu\text{CH}_3)$	4.83	4.82	4.83	4.83	4.83	4.83	

$f(\delta CH_2)$	0.75	0.74	0.75	0.75	0.76	0.75	
$f(\delta CH_3)$	0.52	0.51	0.52	0.52	0.53	0.52	
$f(\delta OH)$	1.05	1.12	1.05	1.14	1.12	1.15	0.81
$f(\delta COO)$	1.34	1.39	1.3395	1.39	1.47	1.43	1.63

Note: Units are $\text{mdyn } \text{\AA}^{-1}$ for stretching and $\text{mdyn } \text{\AA} \text{ rad}^{-2}$ for angle deformations

Source: ^aThis work, ^bFrom Gunasekaran et al. (2005)].

Figure 10. Variations of Scaled Force Constants of Both Forms of Nalidixic Acid in Methanol Solution and Its Dimer by Using the B3LYP/6-311++G Method. Units are $\text{mdyn } \text{\AA}^{-1}$ for Stretching and $\text{mdyn } \text{\AA} \text{ rad}^{-2}$ for Angle Deformations**

Obviously, the higher values for the three species are observed in the $f(\nu C=O)$ force constants, as in similar compounds containing these groups (Keresztury, et al., 1993; Ghalla, et al., 2014). Note that in general the force constants of dimer of acid present lower values than the monomers ones. A very important result is observed in the $f(\nu C-N)_{R1}$ force constants because for the A1 rings which are linked to C=O and COO groups have lower values than the other $f(\nu C-N)_{R2}$ ones. Evidently, those two groups have influence on their values. On the other hand, the N atoms of rings A2 have the lone pairs and lower C-N distances that justify the higher values. The remaining constants are in agreement with the reported in the literature for similar compounds (Romano, et al., 2020; Romani, et al., 2020; Vakili, et al., 2021).

Conclusions

In this study, the B3LYP/6-311++G** level of theory was used to elucidate the optimized monomeric and dimer structures and vibrational infrared of nalidixic acid in gas phase and methanol solution, according to the experimental ones. NBO and AIM calculations have evidenced that both forms present the same stabilities in the gas phase while the form II is less stable in methanol solution. The form I has a solvation energy of -89.22 kJ/mol while the form II -60.34 kJ/mol and the dimer -73.32 kJ/mol . HOMO-LUMO studies show that the form I is most reactive in methanol solution as compared with the form II and its dimer. According to the mapped MEP, the carbonyl and hydroxyl groups are the best electrophilic and nucleophilic places for Nalidixic acid.

The present study confirms some of the assignments previously made (Gunasekaran, et al., 2005; Drlica, et al., 2009) with some

modifications indicated by the most accurate force field developed in the present work.

Full assignments of the 168 normal modes of vibration for the dimer and 81 for the monomers of acid are reported. The complete force field for dimer and the two monomers have been determined, as well as the principal force constants for stretching and deformation modes. This work reveals the existence of intermolecular contacts, as was observed in solid phase and as supported by NBO and topological calculations. Very good correlations between experimental and theoretical IR, Raman and Ultraviolet spectra are obtained. The three spectra evidence the presence of those three forms of acid.

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Author contribution

Mohammad Vakili: Performed experiments and calculations, analysed and interpreted the data, revision. Vahidreza Darugar: Conceived and designed the experiments; contributed reagents, materials, analysed and interpreted the data. Elaheh Valizadeh kakhki: Performed experiments and calculations. Silvia Antonia Brandán: Conceived and designed the experiments; analysed and interpreted the data; wrote the paper.

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Data availability Available when the authors require it.

Conflicts of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest

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